

CHARACTERISTICS OF NEUROLOGICAL DISORDERS IN CHILDREN UNDER 1 YEAR OF AGE BORN TO MOTHERS WHO EXPERIENCED COVID-19

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Abstract. *Coronavirus infection (COVID-19) is an acute infectious disease caused by a novel strain of the virus from the SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus family. It is transmitted through aerosol and droplet mechanisms as well as through contact with contaminated surfaces. The virus exhibits tropism for lung tissue and can manifest in a spectrum ranging from asymptomatic viral carriage to clinically significant forms of the disease, characterized by symptoms of intoxication and inflammatory processes in both the upper and lower respiratory tracts, potentially leading to pneumonia with a risk of developing severe acute respiratory distress syndrome and sepsis [1,3,7].*

Keywords: *SARS-CoV, MERS-CoV, CDC, neurological complications, abdominal ultrasound, pregnancy.*

Both SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV are known to cause severe complications during pregnancy, including the need for endotracheal intubation and intensive care unit admission, and lead to renal failure and death [3, 5]. The mortality rate from SARS-CoV infection among pregnant women is up to 25% [2,6]. To date, little information has been accumulated on the course of coronavirus infection in pregnant women [1,4]. At the same time, the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) have issued interim guidelines for the management of COVID-19, which include some aspects of care for pregnant women [3,4,8]. Basically, these recommendations take into account the experience of pregnancy management gained during previous outbreaks of coronavirus infection. There is currently insufficient and conflicting data on the impact of COVID-19 on pregnant women and infants, and no specific recommendations for pregnant women regarding the diagnosis and treatment of COVID-19. Numerous studies have shown adverse pregnancy outcomes in patients with COVID-19 [7,9]. According to the Swedish Ministry of Health, there is evidence that the risk of hospitalization in intensive care units in pregnant women and women in labor with laboratory-confirmed SARS-CoV-2 in Sweden is higher than in non-pregnant women of the same age [9]. In fact, it is unknown whether the new coronavirus infection suffered at different stages of pregnancy will affect newborns, and whether the children will have the same clinical condition as children born to healthy mothers. The neurological status of children born to mothers who suffered from COVID-19 during pregnancy has not been sufficiently studied. Despite the decline in severe cases and mortality worldwide, mainly due to large-scale vaccination of the population, the SARS-CoV-2 virus continues to circulate and remains a potential threat to vulnerable groups of citizens, including pregnant women [4].

For this reason, this research aims to identify neurological disorders in neonates during the neonatal period, as well as to establish strategies for monitoring, examination, and prevention of

neurological complications in infants born to mothers who experienced COVID-19 at various stages of pregnancy, with an assessment of neurological status at birth.

The aim of the research: To investigate the clinical and neurological characteristics of children under one year of age born to mothers who contracted the novel coronavirus infection (COVID-19) at different stages of pregnancy.

Materials and Methods: The research was conducted from 2022 to 2024 at the outpatient clinic of the Republican Perinatal Center. The study involved 207 newborns, including 112 boys (54.10%) and 95 girls (45.9%). Assessments were carried out at ages 1, 3, 6, 9, and 12 months. The main group (MG) consisted of 105 children, including 8 sets of twins, born to 97 women who had contracted COVID-19 during pregnancy. The diagnosis of COVID-19 in pregnant women occurred in both the first and second/third trimesters. We analyzed the maternal somatic and obstetric-gynecological history, the course of the current pregnancy, delivery outcomes, and the neurological status of newborns up to one year of age. Instrumental methods such as neurosonography and abdominal ultrasound were employed. Data analysis was performed using statistical processing methods. To compare outcomes, complications of pregnancy, and the neurological status of children, a control group (CG) was formed based on a case-control principle. This group included 102 newborns, including 7 sets of twins, born to 95 women with no history of COVID-19.

Inclusion Criteria for the Main Study Group: Children born to mothers who contracted COVID-19 during pregnancy.

Inclusion criteria for the comparative study group: Children born to mothers who did not have a new coronavirus infection COVID-19 during pregnancy.

Criteria for exclusion from the study: children transferred from other institutions. Positive HIV status, hepatitis B, C in the mother.

A comparison was made of the course of the neonatal period in children in the main group and the comparison group. When analyzing the main group of children, they were divided into 3 groups depending on the trimester in which the disease was contracted, and into subgroups depending on the severity of the disease suffered by the mother. The study included 105 newborns. The children were divided into three groups in accordance with the gestational age at which their mothers contracted COVID-19:

Group 1 - 38 children born to 35 mothers who contracted the new coronavirus infection COVID-19 in the first trimester of pregnancy: Subgroup 1a - 29 newborns from 27 mothers who had a mild form of COVID-19; 1b subgroup - 9 newborns from 9 mothers who had COVID-19 in a moderate form;

2 group - 33 children born to 32 mothers who had the new coronavirus infection COVID-19 in the second trimester of pregnancy: 2a subgroup - 22 newborns from 22 mothers who had COVID-19 in a mild form; 2b subgroup - 8 newborns from 8 mothers who had COVID-19 in a moderate form; 2c subgroup - 3 newborns from 3 mothers who had COVID-19 in a severe form;

Group 3 - 34 children born to 30 mothers who had a new coronavirus infection COVID-19 in the third trimester of pregnancy: Subgroup 3a - 23 newborns of 167 mothers who had a mild form of COVID-19, Subgroup 3b - 11 newborns of 11 mothers who had a moderate form of COVID-19.

Results: We studied the features of the course of pregnancy and childbirth in women who had a new coronavirus infection COVID-19. A comparative analysis of the developmental

histories of 105 newborns (main group), born to 97 women who had a new coronavirus infection during pregnancy, as well as the histories of 102 children (comparison group), born to 95 women without COVID-19 during pregnancy was carried out.

When analyzing the main group and the comparison group, among somatic diseases in women in the main group, the most common were chronic arterial hypertension (43%), anemia (77%), urogenital infections (23%), and lipid metabolism disorders (17%). When analyzing other somatic pathologies, no significant difference was found in the study groups. When analyzing the obstetric and gynecological history, it was found that in the main group, miscarriages and/or non-viable pregnancies were significantly more common. The remaining compared indicators were comparable in the comparison groups. The age of women in the main and comparison groups at the time of delivery ranged from 19 to 47 years;

The course of the current pregnancy in women of the observation group had complications in the form of: polyhydramnios 24%, chronic intrauterine hypoxia of the fetus in 14.8%, umbilical cord entanglement in 12.7%, premature placental abruption in 7.4%, dirty waters in 18.9%, early rupture of amniotic fluid in 11.2%, oligohydramnios in 5.4%. However, early rupture of amniotic fluid, umbilical cord entanglement, chronic intrauterine hypoxia of the fetus were significantly more often detected in mothers, newborns born to mothers who had COVID-19 in the first trimester. In addition, mothers who had COVID-19 in the first trimester were more likely to have a threat of termination of pregnancy. During the ultrasound examination conducted during pregnancy, uteroplacental blood flow disorders were diagnosed in 4.3% of women in the main group in groups 1, 2, 3, respectively, and in 3.4% of women in the comparison group. Signs of fetal growth retardation syndrome were noted in 4.1% of the fetus in the main group in groups 1, 2, 3, respectively, and in 2.8% of patients in the comparison group. Due to the high risk of thrombotic complications. When analyzing the frequency of premature births depending on the trimester of pregnancy in which the woman suffered a new coronavirus infection, it was found that COVID-19 infection suffered in the first trimester of pregnancy leads to an increase in the frequency of premature births compared to the disease suffered in the second and third trimesters of pregnancy. The main causes of premature birth were premature rupture of membranes, the development of regular labor, deterioration of the fetus against the background of an aggravated course of pregnancy. The frequency of cesarean section delivery in the study groups did not differ statistically significantly ($p=0.001$).

Assessments of the newborns' condition using the Apgar scale at 1 and 5 minutes of life indicated that the comparison group exhibited higher average scores on the Apgar scale compared to the main group.

Perinatal damage to the nervous system can be of significant importance when evaluating children's health and the risks associated with the development of neurological disorders in the future. During the early neonatal period, 67% of newborns presented deviations in neurological status. A decrease in tendon reflexes and rapid exhaustion of spinal automatism reflexes (support, automatic walking, crawling) were observed 1.5 times more frequently in newborns from the main group. Increased neural excitability was noted 1.4 times more often, while general lethargy was observed 2.3 times more frequently among newborns whose mothers had experienced severe forms of COVID-19.

The incidence of motor disorders was higher in the main group, at 21.7%, compared to 11% in the comparison group. Similarly, the incidence of hypertensive-hydrocephalic syndrome

was more prevalent in the main group (27.3%) than in the comparison group (11%, $p < 0.05$). This statistically significant difference may indicate the role of perinatal damage to the nervous system in the development of neurological complications in children under one year of age born to mothers who had contracted COVID-19. Additionally, autonomic-visceral dysfunctions were more common in the main group (62.9%) than in the comparison group (45%). The prevalence of increased neuro-reflex excitability syndrome was 47.1% in the main group compared to 27% in the comparison group. As observed, children in the main group exhibited a combination of syndromes indicative of perinatal central nervous system damage, suggesting that such damage may lead to a reduction in adaptive mechanisms in the presence of somatic pathology.

Comorbid pathology was observed in both groups. The overall percentage of comorbid pathology in the main group is 62.9%, in the comparison group - 46%, this emphasizes the importance of taking into account comorbidity when assessing the development of neurological complications in children with coronavirus infection, however, when taking into account each pathology separately, the difference between the groups was insignificant. The percentage of cardiac disorders in the main group is 10%, while in the comparison group - 6%, allergic pathology was also more common in the main group (14.3%) compared to the comparison group (12%), as well as the percentage of gastrointestinal diseases in the main group was higher (14.3%) than in the comparison group (6%).

In NSG in patients of the main group, it was found that periventricular leukomalacia (PVL) was present only at birth. In the caudo-thalamic notch, cysts were observed significantly more often in patients of the main group than in the comparison group at birth at 1, 3 and 12 months of age ($p < 0.05$). No significant differences in the incidence of cysts in the caudo-thalamic notch were found in the 6- and 9-month periods ($p > 0.05$). Expansion of the cerebral ventricles (ventriculomegaly), expansion of the subarachnoid space and interhemispheric fissure were observed without significant differences in the observed patients of the groups. There were cysts in the caudo-thalamic notch at the age of one month in 4 (11.4%) patients of the CG, without a significant difference with children of the MG ($p > 0.05$).

Summary:

1. In the main group of women, a history of miscarriages and / or non-developing pregnancy was more often noted compared to women who did not have COVID-19 during pregnancy.

2. When analyzing the frequency of premature births depending on the trimester of pregnancy in which the woman had COVID-19, it was found that a new coronavirus infection suffered in the first trimester of pregnancy more often leads to an increase in the frequency of premature births compared to the disease in the second and third trimesters of pregnancy.

3. Clinical signs of perinatal CNS damage in the form of a fairly clearly defined symptom complex were observed 2 times more often in children born to mothers with Covid-19 infected at different stages of pregnancy.

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